

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Jovihyo****FIRST NAME: Vincent****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of these answers best describes the practice of plagiarism?

- Plagiarism occurs when you use one's word or ideas, works and fail to acknowledge the author.¹**
- Plagiarism occurs when you use one's word or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting from internet and acknowledging the author of such work.
- By acknowledging the author and source of what you have written in your paper and appending your name, you are plagiarizing.
- Plagiarism is an academic art that requires the writer to acknowledge the works from other authors when you include such works in your research.

¹ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> accessed July 29, 2019). 10.

2. **Name the three main sources for data consultation preferentially?**

- Primary data, tertiary data and secondary data.
- Tertiary data, secondary data and primary data.
- Primary data, secondary data and tertiary data.²**
- Secondary data, primary data and tertiary data.

3. **Which of the following statements below clearly explains the significance of citation?**

- To prove that you come across a fine worded piece of work from a reputable author.
- To have a voluminous paper like those authors so as to gain recognition.
- It is good to cite so that your work will look beautiful in the eyes of your readers.
- To give credit to the author, prove the accuracy of our work, show that traditions have been followed and to help our readers to verify.³**

4. **A superscript number has been placed at the end of a sentence, what type of citation is this?**

- Author-date style of citation.

² Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, (Eighth Edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press). 24 & 25.

³ Ibid, 86

- Notes-bibliography style of citation.**⁴
- Author-date and bibliography style of citation.
- Parenthetical style of citation.
5. **Which of these answers gives the six traditions of inquiry that researchers use in conducting their research?**
- Case study, grounded theory, narrative research, Pragmatism, ethnography and postpositivism.
- Case study, grounded theory, narrative research, Pragmatism, ethnography and hermeneutics.
- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative research and hermeneutics.**⁵
- Case study, grounded theory, narrative research, Pragmatism, ethnography and phenomenology.
6. **Which of these statements below best describes trustworthiness in a qualitative research?**

⁴ Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, (Eighth Edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press). 87.

⁵ Bloomberg, Linda D, and Marie Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications). 10, 11 & 12.

- The research must be lengthy that readers will read and trust it because of its volume.
- When there is justification that the researcher is qualified and therefore, can be trusted even though no verification of work is done.
- The research that has the elements of credibility, dependability and transferability.⁶**
- Any research can be trusted if it is voluminous and has resounding research topic and all necessary literature to review.

7. **What are the advantages and disadvantages of footnotes and endnotes?**

- The advantage of footnotes is that they are easily accessible and for endnotes; the writer has enough space to write on a page. The disadvantage of footnotes is that they occupy writable space and for endnotes; readers have to flip forward and back to verify.⁷**
- The advantage is that the footnotes do not end your dissertation, but endnotes complete your dissertation. The disadvantage of footnotes is that they do not occupy most of your space and for endnotes, is that they can terminate your dissertation.
- There are no advantages or disadvantages between the two, hence both are notes and are in the dissertation.
- The advantage of footnotes is that you can easily see them and for endnotes you can see them after all your reading. The disadvantage of footnotes is that they at the foot and for endnotes cannot be reached.

⁶ Bloomberg, Linda D, and Marie Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications). 77 & 78.

⁷ Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, (Eighth Edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press). 95 & 96.

8. **Select the answer that best describes: (a) Introduction, (b) literature review and (c) methodology.**

- (a) Introduction gives the history of the research, (b) Literature review gives literature of the world and (c) methodology proposes the conclusions and recommendations.
- (a) Introduction gives the overview of the research, (b) literature review is studying the available relevant materials and (c) methodology proposes the strategies or methods for the research.⁸**
- (a) Introduction describes the topic and references, (b) Literature review gives an overview of the methods (c) methodology proposes the case studies to be followed.
- (a) Introduction describes the biography and characteristics of the researcher (b) Literature review gives you the efforts made by the researcher reading books and (c) methodology proposes the methods that will make a researcher to gain reputation.

9. **Which of the following statements below best describes the effects of the four schools of thought or paradigms on researchers?**

- Researchers turn to these schools of thought or paradigms for both academic and financial help to collect data.
- They affect researchers based on their ideological theories and as such every researcher decides on which paradigm or paradigms to use.⁹**
- They influence researchers in helping them to write voluminous dissertation in order to be recognized as doctoral graduates.
- They make researchers to be successful writers and equally make them to be recognized the world over.

⁸ Bloomberg, Linda D, and Marie Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications). 16 & 19.

⁹ Ibid, 8, 9 & 10.

10. Choose below the statement that gives you the difference between delimitations and limitations of study?

- Delimitations are where you have no sample or data and limitations indicate where your research will end.
- Delimitations are where there are no boundaries in a research while, limitations restrict the researcher in reviewing certain literature.
- Delimitations clarify the boundaries of your study while limitations are limits marked that terminate the research.
- Delimitations clarify the boundaries of your study and limitations arise as a result of restricted sample size, sample selection and lack of literature.¹⁰**

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¹⁰ Ibid, 78 & 79